

Scalable and Interoperable Data Infrastructure in Energy Domain

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Abstract.

With the increasing complexity, variability, and volume of data, it is becoming increasingly necessary to develop data access approaches that are interoperable and scalable. Traditional data infrastructure based on batch ETL processes lacks the adaptability necessary to meet modern demands, resulting in organizations not achieving optimal business intelligence results. The focus has shifted from collecting data in a centralized environment to connecting with distributed sources in real time. By using technologies such as data virtualization, diverse data types can be accessed, governed and integrated seamlessly across a variety of platforms. Using APIs, Semantic models, and Container technologies can simplify energy research data management and allow us to navigate today's dynamic ecosystems effectively.

Keywords: Data Virtualization, Interoperability, Scalability, ETL/ELT, API, Containerization

1. Introduction

Traditionally, organizations relied on centralized repositories like data warehouses and data lakes for storing and analyzing large datasets. With the advent of cloud services, these systems have been modernized to leverage scalable infrastructures. However, today's data landscape is highly distributed, spanning relational and NoSQL databases, graph databases, files, SaaS services, and more. Consolidating such diverse data into a single repository is impractical and inefficient, leading to operational bottlenecks.

Traditional data lake architectures have key shortcomings. ETL (Extract, Transfer, Load) processes introduce inconsistencies, duplication, and latency, while syncing centralized repositories with distributed sources delays insights. Growing analytical demands require duplicating data, increasing storage and resource consumption. Additionally, regulations like GDPR restrict the movement of sensitive data, necessitating that some remain in place. These issues underscore the need for a paradigm shift in data management [1,2].

To address these challenges, a new paradigm, data virtualization, has emerged, combined with modern ELT pipelines, advanced data management and orchestration tools. Our approach in the NEED project leverages the concept of data virtualization with modern ELT pipelines to provide a robust platform for accessing the required data across diverse data sources. By integrating data management and orchestration tools, RESTful APIs, Service-Based Architecture (SBA), Kubernetes environments, and semantic web technologies, we aim to deliver scalable and interoperable solutions that unify data access without physical consolidation. This approach not only enhances energy data accessibility and governance for research but also

meets the dynamic demands of complex data ecosystems efficiently [3]. In the following sections, we will explore these concepts in greater detail, focusing on how data virtualization and modern technologies overcome the limitations of traditional data infrastructures.

2. Technical Concepts and Architecture

2.1 Data Management and Orchestration Tools

In modern data infrastructures, data management and orchestration tools play a pivotal role in streamlining the processes of extraction, loading, and transformation. These tools enable organizations to build robust ELT pipelines that minimize latency and optimize data workflows. We use **Dagster** for orchestration and **dbt** for transformation [4,5]. Dagster enables the orchestration of data extraction and loading processes, while dbt is leveraged to perform transformations directly in the target system, aligning with the ELT paradigm. This combination ensures a seamless flow of data from source to destination, providing both efficiency and scalability.

2.2 Interoperability

Interoperability is essential for enabling seamless data integration and utilization across systems. Among various approaches proposed to achieve interoperability, including standardization, middleware (adaptors), Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), semantics and data models, model-driven development, and Service-Based Architecture (SBA), in this project APIs, semantics, and SBA play key roles in providing interoperability [6].

- **Application Programming Interfaces (APIs)**

In NEED project, we utilize **FastAPI** to create wrappers in front of diverse data sources. This approach overcomes the differences in data source access methods by standardizing the interface for interacting with these sources. Instead of querying all data sources simultaneously, the API facilitates targeted access, retrieving only the data needed for specific use cases. This design not only enhances efficiency but also simplifies integration with downstream systems.

- **Semantic Web and Service-Based Architecture**

Semantic technologies provide a framework for defining and linking data in a structured and meaningful way, enhancing data discoverability and integration. By combining these with a service-based architecture, the NEED project ensures modularity and scalability. The use of SBA decouples services, allowing for flexible development and deployment of interoperable components that can adapt to evolving requirements.

2.3 Containerization Technology

Containerization technologies like **Docker** and **Kubernetes** are fundamental to achieving scalability and accessibility in modern data infrastructures. In NEED project, Kubernetes orchestrates containerized applications, automating their deployment, scaling, and management. By leveraging a service-based architecture and APIs alongside a message broker, the platform ensures data is accessible from anywhere at any time. This combination provides a resilient and adaptable framework for meeting the demands of diverse and distributed data ecosystems.

2.4 Architecture

In Figure 1, the NEED architecture encompasses ontology-related components, data management and orchestration tools, and data source proxy APIs. Figure 2 shows the procedure, when customers submit a request, the ontology components process it to determine the necessary data sources based on the customer's needs. This request is then converted into a JSON file and transmitted via a messaging protocol to the data orchestrator.

Upon receiving the request, Dagster triggers a new pipeline that interacts with the data source proxy APIs. Using Dagster and dbt, the JSON outputs from each API are normalized, saved into structured tables, and seamlessly integrated. The resulting unified dataset is then delivered to the customer as the final output.

Figure 1: NEED Architecture

Figure 2: Flow chart for raw data collection for various purposes from different sources

Data availability statement

The data used in this project includes **OSM**, **Open-MaStR**, and **ALKIS** [7-9].

Author contributions

Mahsa Faraji Shoyari and Markus Duchon – Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing and Editing

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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